

1 **Title**

2 MUC20 expression marks the receptive phase of the human endometrium

3 **Authors**

4 Artjom Stepanjuk^a, Mariann Koel^{a,b}, Martin Pook^a, Merli Saare^{b,c}, Kersti Jääger^b, Maire Peters^{b,c},
5 Kaarel Krjutškov^{b,d}, Sulev Ingerpuu^a, Andres Salumets^{b,c,e,f}

6 ^aInstitute of Molecular and Cell Biology, University of Tartu, Riia 23, 51010 Tartu, Estonia

7 ^bCompetence Centre on Health Technologies, Tiigi 61b, 50410 Tartu, Estonia

8 ^cDepartment of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Institute of Clinical Medicine, University of Tartu,
9 L. Puusepa 8, 50406 Tartu, Estonia

10 ^dResearch Program of Molecular Neurology, Research Programs Unit, University of Helsinki,
11 and Folkhälsan Institute of Genetics, Haartmaninkatu 8, 00290 Helsinki, Finland

12 ^eDepartment of Biomedicine, Institute of Biomedicine and Translational Medicine, University of
13 Tartu, Ravila 19, 50411 Tartu, Estonia

14 ^fDepartment of Obstetrics and Gynecology, University of Helsinki and Helsinki University
15 Hospital, Haartmaninkatu 2, 00014 Helsinki, Finland

16 **Corresponding author**

17 Andres Salumets

18 Postal address: Tiigi 61b, 50410 Tartu, Estonia

19 E-mail: andres.salumets@ccht.ee

20

21 **Abstract**

22 **Research question:** How does mucin MUC20 expression change during the menstrual cycle in
23 different cell types of human endometrium?

24 **Design:** Study involved examination of MUC20 expression in two previously published RNA-
25 seq datasets in whole endometrial tissue (n=10) and sorted endometrial epithelial (n=44) or
26 stromal (n=42) cell samples. RNA-Seq results were validated by qRT-PCR in whole tissue
27 (n=10), and sorted epithelial (n=17) and stromal (n=17) cell samples. MUC20 protein
28 localisation and expression were analysed in human endometrium by immunohistochemical
29 analysis of intact endometrial tissue (n=6) and also Western blot of cultured stromal and
30 epithelial cells (n=2).

31 **Results:** MUC20 is differentially expressed in the endometrium between the pre-receptive and
32 receptive phases. We show that MUC20 is predominantly expressed by epithelial cells of the
33 receptive endometrium, both at the mRNA (RNA-Seq, P=0.005; qRT-PCR, P=0.039) and
34 protein levels (Western blot; immunohistochemistry, P=0.029).

35 **Conclusion:** Our results indicate to MUC20 as a novel marker of mid-secretory endometrial
36 biology. We propose a model about MUC20 function in the hepatocyte growth factor (HGF)-
37 activated mesenchymal-epithelial transition (MET) receptor signalling specifically in the
38 receptive phase. Further investigations should reveal the precise function of MUC20 in human
39 endometrium and the possible connection between MUC20 and HGF-activated MET receptor
40 signalling. MUC20 could potentially be included in the list of endometrial receptivity markers
41 after further clinical validation.

42

43 **Keywords**

44 Endometrium, Receptivity, Mucin, MUC20, Implantation, Window of implantation

45

46 **Introduction**

47 Successful implantation of a blastocyst to the maternal endometrium is one of the key events
48 during embryonic development. Endometrial tissue cells that respond to hormonal regulation
49 interact with the blastocyst only during a short period during the normal endometrial maturation
50 – 5-6 days after fertilisation (Hertig et al., 1956), which is referred to as a window of
51 implantation (WOI) or a receptivity phase (Psychoyos, 1986). The surface of the endometrial
52 epithelium is the site where the first molecular interactions occur between the trophoblast cells of
53 the implanting embryo and the maternal organism (Enders et al., 1983). However, the molecular
54 mechanisms of the embryo implantation process are still incompletely understood. Although
55 assisted reproductive technologies have been widely used during the last decades, the rate of
56 successful pregnancies among patients who had passed *in vitro* fertilisation (IVF) procedure has
57 not risen. The ability to define the WOI more precisely could significantly improve the
58 pregnancy rate of the IVF procedure.

59

60 Different approaches have been implemented to estimate the WOI in the human endometrium
61 including dating of the endometrial development based on the morphological parameters of
62 endometrial tissue biopsies (Noyes et al., 1950), immunohistological dating with integrated
63 expression scoring of previously known receptivity biomarkers (e.g. $\alpha V\beta 3$ integrin) (Germeyer
64 et al., 2014), and more recently, transcriptomics-based analysis of the differences between pre-
65 receptive and receptive endometrium (Carson et al., 2002; Haouzi et al., 2009; Hu et al., 2014;
66 Sha et al., 2011; Talbi et al., 2006). The commercial endometrial receptivity array (ERA) test
67 uses the expression profiling of 238 pre-defined genes and is currently used in clinical
68 diagnostics (Díaz-Gimeno et al., 2011). Transcriptome-based studies typically suffer from the
69 small overlap between different studies (Altmäe et al., 2014), which can be increased by

70 improved meta-analysis that has the potential to reveal the signature of human endometrial
71 receptivity (Altmäe et al., 2017). However, new molecular markers are needed for more accurate
72 dating of WOI and a deeper understanding of the receptivity mechanisms in human
73 endometrium.

74

75 Mucins are integral components of mucosal surfaces all over the body, having a high variety of
76 functions from the physical protection and lubrication of the epithelial layers to the molecular
77 modulation of immunity and cell signalling (Corfield, 2015; Hattrop and Gendler, 2008). The
78 mucin barrier is hormonally regulated during the menstrual cycle in many mammalian species
79 including humans (Thathiah and Carson, 2002). Mucins form a diverse family of 19 highly
80 glycosylated proteins which are divided into two groups: secreted, and membrane-associated or
81 membrane-tethered types. The uterine membrane-tethered mucins play an essential role during
82 embryo implantation (Thathiah and Carson, 2002). Despite endometrial mucins' potential role in
83 the regulation of receptivity, the only mucin that has been intensively studied in the human
84 endometrium is MUC1 (Aplin *et al.*, 1994; Hey *et al.*, 1994). Only a few studies have mentioned
85 MUC4 and MUC16 in the context of human endometrial receptivity (Dharmaraj et al., 2014;
86 Gipson et al., 2008; Koscinski et al., 2006).

87

88 One of the mucins, MUC20 differs considerably from other members of the mucin family, both
89 by a relatively small size and a low level of glycosylation. This contrasts with other membrane-
90 tethered mucins that are highly glycosylated and can protrude from the cell membrane up to
91 hundreds of nanometers, and form the glycocalyx (Corfield, 2017). MUC20, on the other hand,
92 has an untypically long cytoplasmic tail (Higuchi et al., 2004a). MUC20 was described relatively
93 recently, and its functions in cell physiology are not well known (Higuchi et al., 2004b). In this

94 study, we set out to precisely determine the expression of MUC20 in different endometrial cell
95 types both in the pre-receptive and receptive phases.

96

97 **Materials and methods**

98 **Study participants**

99 The study was approved (19.12.2012) and prolonged (18.12.2017) by the Research Ethics
100 Committee of the University of Tartu (protocol No 221/M-31; prolongation protocol No 276/M-
101 15), also written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Endometrial biopsies were
102 obtained from healthy volunteers at fertile age (≤ 35 years) with normal body mass index (BMI)
103 (within a range of 19-25 kg/m²). All women selected for the study had a regular menstrual cycle,
104 were clinically examined by ultrasound for the absence of visible pelvic pathologies and
105 polycystic ovary syndrome, and had no symptoms or complaints of endometriosis. The levels of
106 testosterone and prolactin, measured from the blood plasma corresponded to the normal values
107 of reproductive age women. The level of progesterone measured from the blood plasma samples
108 collected in the mid-secretory phase of the menstrual cycle corresponded to the expected levels
109 at that cycle phase. The women were non-smokers, were not taking any hormonal treatments for
110 three months prior to the study, had no previous infertility record, and had at least one live-born
111 child. Endometrial biopsies were obtained using a Pipelle catheter (Laboratoire CCD, France) on
112 day 2 and 8 after the luteinizing hormone (LH) surge (LH+2 and LH+8) within the same natural
113 cycle. Menstrual cycle dating was confirmed by combining menstrual cycle history and LH peak
114 estimation by the BabyTime hLH urine cassette (Pharmanova), vaginal ultrasound and
115 histological evaluation of biopsy according to Noyes' criteria (Noyes et al., 1950). Altogether 10
116 women were recruited to detect *MUC1* and *MUC20* expression levels in whole endometrial
117 tissue biopsies and 26 women in sorted endometrial stromal and epithelial cells. The
118 immunohistological evaluation was performed in six additional women.

119

120 Western blot analysis was performed in cultured primary epithelial and stromal cells obtained
121 from two women. For isolation of primary cultures of endometrial epithelial and stromal cells,
122 two separate biopsies were obtained. First endometrial biopsy (proliferative phase, menstrual
123 cycle day 12) was obtained from one 44-year-old woman (reproductive history: 3 pregnancies
124 and 3 deliveries) with endometriosis (III stage) undergoing laparoscopy at the Tartu University
125 Hospital Women's Clinic (Tartu, Estonia). The woman had a regular menstrual cycle (28 ± 5
126 days), body mass index 21 kg/m^2 and used no hormonal medications during the previous three
127 months before laparoscopy. A second endometrial biopsy (early secretory phase, menstrual cycle
128 day 19) was obtained from one 35-year-old woman (reproductive history: 1 pregnancy and 1
129 delivery) with secondary infertility undergoing laparoscopy at the Tartu University Hospital
130 Women's Clinic (Tartu, Estonia). No sign of pelvic abnormalities (no adhesions, normal size of
131 uterus and ovaries) or endometriosis was detected during laparoscopy. The woman had a regular
132 menstrual cycle (28 ± 5 days), body mass index 26 kg/m^2 and used no hormonal medications
133 during the previous three months before laparoscopy. The endometrial biopsy samples were
134 collected during the laparoscopy using an endometrial suction Pipelle catheter (Laboratoire
135 CCD, France).

136

137 **Biopsies processing**

138 The endometrial tissue biopsies for whole tissue study were placed into RNAlater (Ambion Inc.,
139 USA) solution and stored at -80°C for the further analysis. For cell type-specific analysis the
140 endometrial tissue samples were placed immediately into the cryopreservation medium
141 containing $1\times$ Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM, Life Technologies USA), 30%
142 (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS, Biowest, USA), and 7.5% (v/v) Dimethyl Sulfoxide Hybri-Max
143 (Sigma, USA). The cryovials were put into a Nalgene Cryo 1°C "Mr. Frosty" Freezing Container

144 (Thermo Scientific, USA) and placed into -80°C freezer overnight. The biopsies were stored in
145 liquid nitrogen until use. Total RNA from whole tissue was extracted by using miRNeasy Mini
146 kit following the manufacturer's protocol (Qiagen, Germany). The endometrial biopsys'
147 handling, dissociation, and preparation for the fluorescence-activated cell sorting (FACS) has
148 been described in detail (Krijtškov et al., 2016). Briefly, the biopsied tissue samples were
149 thawed, dissociated, and endometrial cells were stained with fluorochrome-conjugated antibodies
150 (Imai et al., 1992; Kato et al., 2007). Stromal cells were stained with mouse anti-human CD13
151 monoclonal antibody (clone TUK1, R-Phycoerythrin, Invitrogen, USA), epithelial cells were
152 stained simultaneously with the fluorochrome-conjugated mouse anti-human CD9 monoclonal
153 antibody (clone MEM-61, FITC, Novus Biologicals, USA) and all dead cells were stained with
154 DAPI (Invitrogen, USA). CD9 or CD13 positive and DAPI negative (alive) cells were sorted
155 directly into QIAzol Lysis Reagent (Qiagen, Germany). Total RNA was isolated immediately
156 using RNeasy Micro kit (Qiagen, Germany). The paired samples of (LH+2) and (LH+8)
157 endometrial tissue biopsies from six healthy volunteers were used in immunohistochemistry.
158 Tissue samples for histological assessment and immunohistochemical analysis were fixed and
159 stored in the 10% formalin solution. All samples used in our study including two separate
160 biopsies for Western blot analysis are noted on the simplified menstrual cycle scheme (Fig. 1).

161

162 **Transcriptome data analysis**

163 We used two of our previously published RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) datasets to determine the
164 expression of mucins in the whole endometrium and in sorted epithelial and stromal LH+2 and
165 LH+8 endometrial cells (Altmäe et al., 2017). Both datasets are accessible via Gene Expression
166 Omnibus (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/) under accession numbers GSE98386 and GSE97929,
167 respectively. The paired-end 100 bp sequencing on Illumina HiSeq2500 instrument was used for
168 transcriptome profiling for whole tissue samples (GSE98386) for 10 women, as described in our

169 previous study (Altmäe et al., 2017). The cell-type specific RNA-seq analysis was performed
170 with sorted epithelial and stromal cells (GSE97929) for 26 women, as also described in the same
171 study (Altmäe et al., 2017), following our single-cell tagged reverse transcription (STRT)
172 protocol (Krjutškov et al., 2016) with modifications for bulk RNA. In data analysis, pre-
173 processing and differential transcriptome expression analyses were performed with STRTprep
174 pipeline (v3dev branch, available at <https://github.com/shka/STRTprep>). This pipeline makes use
175 of the SAMstrt package (Katayama et al., 2013) utilising the variation of SAM (significance
176 analysis of microarrays) statistical test which is adjusted to RNA-seq data (Li and Tibshirani,
177 2011). As this is a non-parametrical statistical test, this is more robust to outliers and to the
178 deviations from the assumptions of parametrical methods (Li and Tibshirani, 2011).

179

180 **Quantitative reverse transcription qRT-PCR**

181 The *MUC1* and *MUC20* expression levels in whole endometrial biopsies were determined in ten
182 paired LH+2 and LH+8 endometrial samples. Cell type-specific expression pattern was
183 determined in seventeen out of the 26 paired (LH+2 and LH+8) endometrial epithelial and
184 stromal cell samples isolated by FACS method described before (Krjutškov et al., 2016). DNase
185 treated (TURBO DNA-free™ kit, Ambion Inc., USA) RNA was converted into cDNA using
186 RevertAid First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (Thermo-Fisher Scientific Inc., USA). qRT-PCR
187 was performed using 1 × HOT FIREPol EvaGreen qPCR Mix Plus (Solis BioDyne, Estonia)
188 according to conditions specified by the manufacturer. The following primers were used: MUC1
189 (Rev- TACCTGCAGAAACCTTCTCATAGG, Fw- CATCTTTCCAGCCCGGGATAC) and
190 MUC20 (Rev- CACGCAGTAAGGAGACCTGG, Fw- CGTGAGTGCAGGTGAAAATGG).
191 The succinate dehydrogenase complex subunit A (SDHA: Rev-
192 CCACCACTGCATCAAATTCATG, Fw- TGGGAACAAGAGGGCATCTG) was used as
193 endogenous control. The expression differences between LH+2 and LH+8 were calculated using

194 Welch two-sample t-test, and a p-value cut-off of $p < 0.05$. The $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method was used for
195 calculating the relative expression and the fold change between LH+2 and LH+8 samples (Livak
196 and Schmittgen, 2001).

197

198 **RNA interference (RNAi) mediated knock-down of MUC20**

199 Three unique 27mer siRNA duplexes specific to human MUC20 and scrambled control siRNA
200 (OriGene, USA) were transfected into epidermoid carcinoma cell line (A431) by using
201 HiPerFect transfection reagent (Qiagen, Germany). A431 cell line was obtained from the
202 American Type Culture Collection (ATCC). Transfection complexes were formed according to
203 the manufacturer's instructions. On the day of transfection (0 h), 75,000 cells were seeded into
204 each well of 24-well cell culture plate in 500 μ l Iscove's modified Dulbecco's medium (IMDM
205 medium, Lonza, Switzerland) containing 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS, PAN Biotech,
206 Germany) and antibiotics mix suitable for cell culture (Penicillin (100 U/ml)/Streptomycin (0.1
207 mg/ml), Naxo, Estonia). Immediately after seeding, freshly formed transfection complexes were
208 added drop-wise to the cells. The final concentration of siRNA was 7.5 nM. Next day (24 h) the
209 culture medium was changed with fresh medium without complexes. Subsequently (48 h), cells
210 were passaged 1:2 and transfected for the second time with the same protocol that was used for
211 the first transfection. Next day (72 h), cells were lysed in RIPA buffer containing 10 mM Tris-
212 HCl (pH 7.2), 150 mM NaCl, 0.1% (w/v) SDS, 1% (v/v) Triton X-100, 1% (w/v) sodium
213 deoxycholate, 5 mM EDTA and Complete protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche Diagnostics,
214 Switzerland) and stored at -80°C .

215

216 **Cell culture**

217 For isolation of primary cultures, the cryopreserved endometrial biopsy samples were thawed
218 and washed twice with Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM medium, Life
219 Technologies, USA). The isolation and culturing of endometrial primary stromal and epithelial
220 cells were performed as described previously by Chen and Roan with minor modifications (Chen
221 and Roan, 2015). In our protocol, the primary endometrial epithelial cells were plated on
222 fibronectin-coated (Sigma Aldrich, 20 µg / 2ml / 25cm²) flasks and trypsin-based detaching
223 method was used for both, stromal and epithelial cells. The first passage of primary epithelial
224 cells and the second passage of stromal cells were used for protein isolation. MCF-7 cell line, a
225 human breast cancer cell line, was obtained from ATCC and cultured in DMEM (DMEM-11A,
226 Capricorn Scientific, Germany) with 10% (v/v) FBS (PAN Biotech, Germany) and cell culture
227 antibiotics (Penicillin (100 U/ml)/Streptomycin (0.1 mg/ml), Naxo, Estonia). MCF-7 cell line
228 lysate was used as a negative control for MUC20 protein expression in Western blot
229 experiments. The A431 cell line was obtained from ATCC and cultured in IMDM (Lonza,
230 Switzerland) with 10% (v/v) FBS (PAN Biotech, Germany) and antibiotics (Penicillin (100
231 U/ml)/Streptomycin (0.1 mg/ml), Naxo, Estonia). Cell lines were cultured in the presence of 5%
232 CO₂ at 37°C in humid conditions and passaged with 0.25% Trypsin-EDTA (Naxo, Estonia).
233 Cells were lysed in RIPA buffer containing 10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.2), 150 mM NaCl, 0.1%
234 (w/v) SDS, 1% (v/v) Triton X-100, 1% (w/v) sodium deoxycholate, 5 mM EDTA and Complete
235 protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche Diagnostics, Switzerland) and stored at -80°C.

236

237 **SDS-PAGE and Western blotting**

238 The protein concentration of samples in RIPA were measured with BCA Protein Assay Kit
239 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), and equal protein amounts for each sample were loaded onto
240 4-10% gradient SDS-PAGE gels for electrophoresis (Mini-Protean system, Bio-Rad
241 Laboratories, USA). The material was transferred to polyvinylidene difluoride membrane with

242 Mini Trans-Blot Cell system (Bio-Rad Laboratories, USA). The membrane was washed with
243 1×TBS-T (Tris-Buffered Saline + 0.1% (v/v) Tween 20) and blocked with 2% (w/v) bovine
244 serum albumin (Capricorn Scientific, Germany) dissolved in TBS-T (blocking solution) for 1 h
245 followed by incubation with primary anti-MUC20 antibody (0.5 µg/ml, ab73043, Abcam, UK) in
246 blocking solution overnight at 4°C. After washings with TBS-T, additional blocking with 2%
247 (v/v) normal goat serum in TBS-T was performed for 30 min. After that, the membrane was
248 incubated with the respective secondary goat antibody (Santa-Cruz Biotechnology Inc., USA)
249 conjugated with horseradish peroxidase (HRP) for 1 h at room temperature. Finally, the
250 membrane was rinsed three times with TBS-T for 15 min followed by incubation with
251 Immobilon Western Chemiluminescent HRP Substrate solution (Millipore Corporation, USA).
252 Chemiluminescent signal was detected with BioSpectrum 510 Imaging System with
253 VisionWorks LS software (both UVP, LLC, USA).

254

255 **Immunohistochemistry**

256 For immunohistochemical (IHC) experiments, 4 µm sections from paraffin-embedded tissue
257 blocks were mounted on Superfrost Plus (Thermo Scientific, USA) slides. Tissue sections on
258 slides were deparaffinized and rehydrated according to the standard protocol (Abcam IHC
259 guide). Subsequently, sections were subjected to the antigen retrieval procedure. For antigen
260 retrieval, slides were heated at 60°C for 16 hours in 10 mM Na-citrate buffer (pH 6.0) with
261 0.05% (v/v) Tween 20 (Naxo, Estonia). After antigen retrieval, slides were cooled down to room
262 temperature and washed with tap water for 10 min. All following washing steps were performed
263 using 1×Tris-buffered saline (TBS) with 0.025% (v/v) Triton X-100 (PanReac AppliChem,
264 Germany) as a washing buffer. For the IHC procedure, a mouse and rabbit specific HRP/DAB
265 (ABC) detection kit (ab64264, Abcam, UK) was used. All steps were performed according to the
266 producer's protocol with only a few modifications. After protein blocking and washing steps, we

267 applied additional blocking against possible tissue endogenous biotin. For that purposes the
268 endogenous avidin-biotin blocking system (ab3387, Abcam, UK) was used. Mouse polyclonal
269 antibodies at concentration 5µg/ml, obtained by immunisation against the full-length protein
270 (ab73043, Abcam, UK), were used as primary anti-MUC20 antibodies in IHC. Mouse IgG₁
271 (MAB002), IgG_{2A} (MAB003), IgG_{2B} (MAB0041), and IgG₃ (MAB007) subclasses (all from
272 R&D Systems, USA) were mixed and used for isotype control at the same concentrations as the
273 primary antibody. Incubation with primary antibody and mouse non-specific IgG subclasses was
274 performed overnight in a humidity chamber at 4°C. For antibody dilution and incubation 1×TBS
275 buffer with 1% (w/v) BSA (Capricorn Scientific, Germany) was used. After incubation with the
276 primary antibody, we performed an additional blocking step with 4% (v/v) normal goat serum
277 (Abcam, UK) diluted in 1×TBS buffer. Further steps were performed as per manufacturer's
278 protocol. Chromogenic reaction was developed for 6 min and stopped after that. Cell nuclei were
279 counterstained with Mayer's haematoxylin solution during 1 min, and slides were then washed
280 10 min with tap water. Slides were dehydrated through 30 sec incubation in different ethanol and
281 xylene solutions in opposite order of the rehydration step. Cover glasses were mounted with
282 Eukitt (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) quick-hardening medium. Slides were investigated under an
283 Olympus BX41 microscope with 10×, and 40× magnification objectives and tissue microphotos
284 were taken with an Olympus DP71 camera and Cell B (Olympus, Japan) software. Semi-
285 quantitative analysis of IHC (n=6) was performed with ImageJ package Fiji version 1.52e
286 (Schindelin et al., 2012). DAB signal intensity was measured separately for epithelial and
287 stromal components of the endometrium. The relative DAB intensity was calculated according to
288 the formula: $f=255-i$, where f – relative DAB intensity, i – mean DAB intensity obtained from
289 the software; i ranges from 0 (zero – deep brown, highest expression), and 255 (total white). The
290 method we used for the signal intensity measurements with ImageJ has been previously
291 described for endometrial histological evaluation and consists of 10 image analysis steps that are
292 precisely described in following publication (Fuhrich et al., 2013).

293

294 **Statistical analysis**

295 Mann-Whitney' test or Welch two-sample t-test was used to assess gene expression for
296 significant differences between the pre-receptive (LH+2) and receptive (LH+8) phases using
297 RNA-seq or qRT-PCR data, respectively. For correlation analysis, the changes in the *MUC20*
298 gene expression ($\log_2(\text{fold-change})$) between LH+2 and LH+8) were compared with the changes
299 in expression of other epithelial cells' genes. For that purpose, we used Spearman correlation test
300 (Bonferroni corrected $P < 0.05$, $R > 0.8$). The enrichment of receptivity biomarkers in the human
301 genome or in the *MUC20*-correlated gene subset was compared using Fisher's exact test.
302 Statistical analyses and graphs were made in R (version 3.5.0). For semi-quantitative IHC
303 analysis, DAB signal intensities were compared using paired t-test with a statistically significant
304 p-value cut-off of $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis and graph were prepared in Microsoft Office Excel
305 (365 ProPlus, version 1809).

306

307 **Results**

308 **Endometrial epithelial cells express higher level of *MUC20* mRNA in the receptive than in** 309 **the pre-receptive endometrium**

310 To determine the repertoire of mucins that are expressed in different cell compartments of the
311 human endometrium, we used two of our previously published RNA-seq datasets (GSE97929
312 and GSE98386) and profiled transcriptome expression either separately in stromal and epithelial
313 cells (GSE97929), or in the whole endometrial tissue (GSE98386) during the pre-receptive
314 (LH+2) and receptive (LH+8) phases (Altmäe et al., 2017). Cell-type specific RNA sequencing
315 data (GSE97929) revealed the expression of eight different mucin mRNAs: *MUC1*, *MUC6*,
316 *MUC13*, *MUC15*, *MUC20* and *MUC22* in stromal cells, and *MUC1*, *MUC4*, *MUC7*, *MUC13*,

317 *MUC15*, *MUC20* and *MUC22* in epithelial cells (Table 1). *MUC6* and *MUC7* were only detected
318 in one stromal or one epithelial sample, respectively. The majority of detected mucins were
319 expressed only in 1-8 out of 18 analysed LH+2 stage or 1-14 out of 26 analysed LH+8 epithelial
320 cell samples. *MUC1* was expressed in most of the epithelial samples analysed irrespective of the
321 day (15/18 at LH+2; 24/26 at LH+8). In contrast, while *MUC20* was expressed only in 5 out of
322 18 epithelial samples on day LH+2, most samples (23/26) became positive for *MUC20*
323 expression on day LH+8. Therefore, unlike *MUC1*, *MUC20* displayed a remarkable change in
324 expression between the pre-receptive and receptive phases. Next, the expression levels of *MUC1*
325 and *MUC20* were studied further in the analysed cell-specific samples and provided as RNA-seq
326 normalised read counts in Supplementary Table 1. *MUC1* expression was similar between the
327 LH+2 and LH+8 endometria both within the epithelial and stromal cell populations (Fig. 2).
328 When we compared *MUC1* expression between epithelial and stromal cells in LH+2 and LH+8
329 phases, it appeared that *MUC1* expression was significantly higher in epithelial cells irrespective
330 of the cycle day (P=0.005 at LH+2 and P=0.006 at LH+8). In contrast, the expression of *MUC20*
331 was significantly higher in the LH+8 cycle phase compared with LH+2 in the epithelial cells
332 (P=0.005). Since we detected *MUC20* expression only in 2 samples out of 20 in early-secretory
333 (LH+2) stromal cells (Table 1), we could not compare *MUC20* expression between different
334 phases in stromal cells. Further, the expression level of *MUC1* and *MUC20* was compared in the
335 whole endometrium RNA-seq dataset (GSE98386). In the whole endometrial tissue (n=10)
336 *MUC1* expression was not statistically different between the LH+2 and LH+8, whereas *MUC20*
337 expression was significantly higher in the receptive LH+8 endometrium (P=7.58×10⁻⁵, Mann-
338 Whitney' test). *MUC1* and *MUC20* normalised read counts in whole tissue samples are given in
339 Supplementary Table 1.

340

341 The expression of *MUC1* and *MUC20* was validated by qRT-PCR both in the whole tissue and
342 in the sorted endometrial epithelial and stromal cells (Fig. 3). Our results were in good

343 correspondence with RNA-seq data, showing that *MUC1* expression was significantly higher in
344 epithelial cells compared with stromal cells in both cycle phases ($P=3.4\times 10^{-4}$ at LH+2; $P=0.006$
345 at LH+8). Importantly, qRT-PCR analysis confirmed that *MUC20* expression differed between
346 LH+2 and LH+8 phases in the whole endometrium ($P=1.1\times 10^{-4}$) and in epithelial cells
347 ($P=0.039$). Again, we did not see *MUC20* expression to be significantly different between
348 different cycle days in stromal cells. We also noticed that *MUC20* expression was remarkably
349 higher in epithelial cells than in stromal cells specifically in the receptive (LH+8) phase
350 ($P=0.002$). Taken together, our results demonstrate that the *MUC20* transcription is increased in
351 epithelial cells during the transition from the pre-receptive to the receptive phase.

352

353 **MUC20 protein is expressed predominantly in endometrial epithelial cells**

354 Next, we aimed to confirm whether the expression of MUC20 seen at the mRNA level in
355 epithelial and stromal cells is the same at the protein level. MUC20 protein expression was
356 analysed by Western blot in cultured primary epithelial and stromal cells. Both cell types were
357 isolated from two endometrial biopsies. One collected on menstrual cycle day 12 which
358 corresponds to the end of the proliferative phase (close to LH+2) and other on menstrual cycle
359 day 19 which corresponds to the beginning of the mid-secretory phase (close to LH+8) (Fig. 1).
360 We used an anti-MUC20 antibody, which we validated in epidermoid carcinoma cell line A431
361 that is known to express MUC20, by using RNAi-mediated silencing of MUC20 (Fig. 4A). We
362 transfected A431 cells with three different siRNAs against *MUC20* in parallel with a scrambled
363 control siRNA and detected MUC20 expression by Western blot analysis. We observed a notable
364 decrease in the expression of MUC20 at 95-130 kDa in A431 cells with all siRNAs, strongly
365 suggesting that the anti-MUC20 antibody used specifically recognises MUC20. Next, we
366 detected MUC20 expression separately in cultured endometrium-derived epithelial and stromal
367 cells using A431 cells as a positive and breast adenocarcinoma cell line MCF-7 as a negative

368 control (Fig. 4B). MUC20 protein was expressed at a much higher level in the epithelial cells
369 compared with stromal cells derived from both biopsies (cycle day 12 and 19). MUC20
370 expression in epithelial cells cultured from cycle day 12 biopsy seems to be weaker than from
371 cycle day 19. As we had only one sample from cycle day (cd) 12 (close to LH+2) and one
372 sample from cd 19 (close to LH+8) this was not enough for statistical analysis. However, from
373 these two biopsies we see that cycle phase-independent MUC20 protein expression is higher in
374 the epithelial cells (Fig. 4B). The nearly undetectable expression of MUC20 in stromal cells in
375 Western blot analysis also coincides well with the low level of its transcript in stromal cells
376 irrespective of the cycle day (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). Thus, we conclude that the epithelial cells are
377 the major source of MUC20 protein in the endometrium.

378

379 **Immunohistological detection of MUC20 localisation in the endometrium in the pre-** 380 **receptive and receptive phases**

381 Next, we set out to determine the localisation of MUC20 expression in the intact endometrial
382 tissue using immunohistochemistry (IHC). The endometrial tissue was isolated from six healthy
383 women both at cycle days LH+2 and LH+8. Only very slight, almost undetectable MUC20
384 expression was detected in the endometrial tissue sections in the pre-receptive phase (Fig. 5A, C,
385 E), which was remarkably increased in the receptive phase. The expression of MUC20 was
386 stronger particularly in the glandular and luminal epithelial cell compartments (Fig. 5B, D, F),
387 and less so in the stromal compartment at LH+8. The semi-quantitative analysis confirmed that
388 MUC20 expression is increased at the LH+8 stage compared with the LH+2 in the endometrial
389 epithelial cells (n=6, P=0.029), while stromal MUC20 expression was similar between these two
390 stages (Fig. 5I). These results confirm that MUC20 expression is markedly higher in the
391 receptive than in the pre-receptive endometrial epithelium.

392

393 ***MUC20* expression is correlated with other receptivity biomarkers**

394 To identify the genes that change expression together with *MUC20* in the epithelial cells
395 between the pre-receptive (LH+2) and receptive phases (LH+8), we analysed the transcriptome
396 expression of the epithelial cells from our previous cell-specific RNA-seq dataset (GSE97929)
397 (Altmäe et al., 2017). We found 386 genes whose expression was highly correlated with *MUC20*
398 (Spearman correlation test; Bonferroni corrected $P < 0.05$, $R > 0.8$; Supplementary Table 2).
399 Importantly, we found among the differentially expressed genes several previously known
400 endometrial-epithelial receptivity marker genes including *DPP4*, *TSPAN8*, *CP*, *COMP*, *LAMB3*,
401 *ANXA4* and *ARID5B* (Supplementary Table 2). Moreover, receptivity biomarkers were 7.98
402 times over-represented among *MUC20*-correlated genes compared with the rest of the protein-
403 coding genes in the human genome (Fisher's exact test, two-sided $P = 6.47 \times 10^{-5}$). This finding
404 verifies the receptive phase-specific expression of *MUC20* in the human endometrium.

405

406 **A model of *MUC20* interaction with the MET pathway in the receptive endometrium**

407 MET (mesenchymal-epithelial transition) receptor mediates stromal cell-secreted hepatocyte
408 growth factor (HGF)-signalling that is important for epithelial proliferation and survival (Bottaro
409 et al., 1991; Montesano et al., 1991; Rubin et al., 1991). It has been shown that *MUC20* can
410 interact with the cytoplasmic tail of the MET receptor that results in the suppression of epithelial
411 proliferation (Higuchi et al., 2004a). Therefore, we decided to use cell-type specific RNA
412 sequencing data (GSE97929) to investigate changes in *MET* expression between the pre-
413 receptive LH+2 and receptive LH+8 endometrium. We found that *MET* expression was highly
414 correlated with the *MUC20* expression in endometrial epithelial cells (Spearman correlation test;
415 Bonferroni corrected $P = 0.000994$, $R = 0.898$; Supplementary Table 2). Moreover, we identified
416 that the expression of both HGF mRNA in stromal cells and MET mRNA in epithelial cells
417 increased during the transition between the pre-receptive and receptive phases (Fig. 6). Such

418 synchronous changes in the expression of MUC20 and MET in the epithelium and HGF in the
419 stroma between the LH+2 and LH+8 phases raises the possibility that MUC20 could function in
420 blocking MET-mediated signalling pathway during the WOI.

421

422 **Discussion**

423 Our study has identified increased MUC20 expression in the receptive endometrium epithelium,
424 and we propose it as a new promising biomarker candidate of endometrial receptivity that needs
425 to be validated further to prove its ability to define the WOI. High expression of *MUC1* already
426 in the pre-receptive phase has been previously reported (Aplin et al., 2001). Our results coincide
427 with an earlier study, which detected *MUC1* expression both in the pre-receptive and receptive
428 phases, thus not allowing us to distinguish between different cycle days based on *MUC1*
429 expression (Jeschke et al., 2009).

430

431 *MUC20* mRNA expression has been once documented in the endometrial tissue using
432 microarray-based gene expression analysis (Evans et al., 2012). However, information about
433 MUC20 protein expression in the human endometrium is completely lacking. Here, we provide
434 clear evidence that unlike *MUC1*, *MUC20* expression is dynamically regulated during the
435 menstrual cycle. We detected a significant increase in *MUC20* expression during the transition
436 from the pre-receptive to the receptive phase of the endometrium. This change also occurred at
437 the protein level, and more importantly, differential expression of MUC20 protein was
438 specifically detected in the endometrial epithelium. Strikingly, *MUC20* expression was
439 correlated well with other epithelial receptivity markers. The previously defined receptivity
440 biomarkers (Altmäe et al., 2017) were almost eight times over-represented among *MUC20*
441 correlated genes against the whole human genome. MUC20 expression correlation with
442 previously known receptivity markers does not automatically mean that MUC20 itself plays an

443 important role in the receptivity process, to reveal that, further clinical validation and functional
444 studies are crucial. However, MUC20 coexpression with other endometrial receptivity markers
445 verifies that MUC20 expression is receptive phase-specific in human endometrium. Thus, this
446 knowledge is essential if we think about more precise dating of the implantation window. From
447 an endometrial dating perspective, it is crucial that MUC20 expression is increased in the
448 receptive endometrium, but if we want to compare it with currently used markers bigger cohorts
449 of patients need to be analysed in the clinical validation studies. However, some limitations of
450 our study should also be highlighted. In our study, we showed that both epithelial MUC20
451 mRNA and protein levels change when the endometrial tissue becomes receptive. As post-
452 receptive endometrial samples were not available for this study, it is impossible to say whether
453 the MUC20 expression declines or remains at the same level until the onset of menstruation. We
454 are unable to provide data on whether the receptivity marker MUC20 may be altered in different
455 patient groups, where the endometrial receptivity is affected. Also, the benefit of MUC20 in
456 clinical settings can only be confirmed if data concerning embryo transfer success is
457 ascertained in an appropriately designed trial. Furthermore, we acknowledge that the sample size
458 of our study is relatively low and we cannot entirely exclude the presence of undiagnosed
459 asymptomatic endometriosis cases among the control women, that may theoretically bias the
460 conclusions of the current study.

461

462 Until now, the physiological function of MUC20 which is not related to cancer has been
463 described in kidney cells. It has been shown that MUC20 participates in the regulation of HGF-
464 activated MET receptor-mediated pathway in the renal tubule epithelium (Higuchi et al., 2004a).
465 Stromal cells resident in a wide variety of different tissues are producing HGF that is utilised by
466 epithelial cells via MET receptor (Bottaro et al., 1991; Montesano et al., 1991; Rubin et al.,
467 1991). We found that the expression of *MET* in the epithelium and *HGF* in the stroma increased
468 in the receptive endometrium compared with the pre-receptive endometrium. Moreover, *MET*

469 expression was highly correlated with *MUC20* expression in the epithelial cells. Consistently, the
470 up-regulation of *MET* mRNA during the WOI has been previously observed by others (Evans et
471 al., 2012).

472

473 Previously, it has been shown that MUC20 interaction with the MET receptor blocks a signalling
474 cascade leading to the inhibition of cell proliferation (Fig. 7A). However, this interaction does
475 not affect cell scattering, morphogenesis and cell survival (Higuchi et al., 2004a). We propose a
476 similar function of MUC20 to be present in the human receptive endometrium at a time when the
477 proliferation rate of the epithelial cells slows down (Fig. 7B). Although this hypothesis is
478 intriguing, we cannot provide any direct support for it, because it is difficult to establish the
479 experimental model to prove this claim. It is well known that the endometrial primary epithelial
480 cells are difficult to maintain in culture, and their passage is often limited to only single passage
481 (Chen et al., 2016; Kyo et al., 2003; Masuda et al., 2016). As epithelial cells are highly
482 differentiated, strongly self-adherent and have to be polarised to maintain apical/basolateral
483 morphology, the culturing of these cells is much more difficult compared with their stromal
484 counterparts, mostly because of their limited expansion potential and extremely short life-span.
485 This is the reason why we were unable to apply our MUC20 knock-down protocol in these
486 demanding cells. Endometrial epithelial cell lines like Ishikawa, HEC-1A or RL95-2 are also not
487 suitable as a model for studying the functions of MUC20 in endometrial receptivity because of
488 their cancerous origin. In different types of cancers and particularly endometrial cancers mucins
489 expression is aberrant and MUC20 is no exception from that, as overexpression of MUC20 in
490 endometrial cancers is known to lead to the more malignant and aggressive phenotype (Chen et
491 al., 2013; Zheng et al., 2019).

492

493 Due to the aforementioned difficulties in controlling our hypothesis in the endometrial model,
494 we can only rely on a recent functional study on pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma cells where
495 MUC20 was silenced. Co-immunoprecipitation revealed the physical association of MUC20 and
496 MET. Moreover, MUC20 silencing suppressed the MET/HGF induced malignant phenotype
497 (e.g., high proliferation and viability, migration, invasion) of cancer cells (Chen et al., 2018).
498 That coincides well with our hypothesis that MUC20 and MET also interact in human
499 endometrium, but at the moment we only have indirect confirmation of our hypothesis, and we
500 do not know exact mechanisms of that interaction due to difficulties in performing MUC20
501 knock-down or other functional studies using primary endometrial epithelial cells. However, our
502 model of potential interaction of MUC20 and MET in the receptive endometrium is also
503 supported by an interactome study of human embryo implantation that speculated on the
504 potential function of signalling networks within the endometrial tissue (Altmäe et al., 2012).

505

506 To conclude, to our knowledge this is the first study to report the cycle-dependent expression of
507 *MUC20* in the human endometrium both at mRNA and protein levels. An implication of this
508 study is the possibility that MUC20 could be included in the list of endometrial receptivity
509 markers after further precise clinical validation. Maybe that will help us to determine better the
510 endometrial receptivity status in the future. However, further investigation should also reveal the
511 exact connection between MUC20 and HGF-activated MET receptor signalling in the human
512 endometrium or disprove our hypothesis.

513

514 **Acknowledgements**

515 The authors would like to thank Külli Samuel from the Competence Centre on Health
516 Technologies for the assistance with cell cultures and biopsy samples processing.

517

518 **Funding**

519 This work was supported by the Estonian Ministry of Education and Research (grant no IUT34-
520 16); by the Enterprise Estonia (grant no EU48695); by the EU FP7-PEOPLE-2012-IAPP project
521 SARM (grant no EU324509); by the European Commission Horizon 2020 research and
522 innovation programme under grant agreement 692065 (project WIDENLIFE); and MSCA-RISE-
523 2015 project MOMENDO (grant no 691058).

524

525 **Declaration of interests**

526 The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests that could be perceived as prejudicing the
527 impartiality of the research reported.

528

529

530 **References**

531 Altmäe, S., Esteban, F.J., Stavreus-Evers, A., Simón, C., Giudice, L., Lessey, B.A., Horcajadas,
532 J.A., Macklon, N.S., D’Hooghe, T., Campoy, C., Fauser, B.C., Salamonsen, L.A., Salumets,
533 A., 2014. Guidelines for the design, analysis and interpretation of “omics” data: Focus on
534 human endometrium. *Hum. Reprod. Update* 20, 12–28.
535 <https://doi.org/10.1093/humupd/dmt048>

536 Altmäe, S., Koel, M., Võsa, U., Adler, P., Suhorutšenko, M., Laisk-Podar, T., Kukushkina, V.,
537 Saare, M., Velthut-Meikas, A., Krjutškov, K., Aghajanova, L., Lalitkumar, P.G., Gemzell-
538 Danielsson, K., Giudice, L., Simón, C., Salumets, A., 2017. Meta-signature of human
539 endometrial receptivity: a meta-analysis and validation study of transcriptomic biomarkers.

540 Sci. Rep. 7, 10077. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-10098-3>

541 Altmäe, S., Reimand, J., Hovatta, O., Zhang, P., Kere, J., Laisk, T., Saare, M., Peters, M., Vilo,
542 J., Stavreus-Evers, A., Salumets, A., 2012. Research Resource: Interactome of Human
543 Embryo Implantation: Identification of Gene Expression Pathways, Regulation, and
544 Integrated Regulatory Networks. *Mol. Endocrinol.* 26, 203–217.
545 <https://doi.org/10.1210/me.2011-1196>

546 Aplin, J.D., Meseguer, M., Simón, C., Ortíz, M.E., Croxatto, H., Jones, C.J., 2001. MUC1,
547 glycans and the cell-surface barrier to embryo implantation. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* 29, 153–
548 6. <https://doi.org/10.1042/0300-5127:0290153>

549 Aplin, J.D., Seif, M.W., Graham, R.A., Hey, N.A., Behzad, F., Campbell, S., 1994. The
550 Endometrial Cell Surface and Implantation: Expression of the Polymorphic Mucin MUC-1
551 and Adhesion Molecules during the Endometrial Cycle. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 734, 103–
552 121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.1994.tb21739.x>

553 Bottaro, D.P., Rubin, J.S., Faletto, D.L., Chan, a M., Kmieciak, T.E., Vande Woude, G.F.,
554 Aaronson, S. a, 1991. Identification of the hepatocyte growth factor receptor as the c-met
555 proto-oncogene product. *Science* 251, 802–804. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1846706>

556 Carson, D.D., Lagow, E., Thathiah, A., Al-Shami, R., Farash-Carson, M.C., Vernon, M., Yuan,
557 L., Fritz, M.A., Lessey, B., 2002. Changes in gene expression during the early to mid-luteal
558 (receptive phase) transition in human endometrium detected by high-density microarray
559 screening. *Mol. Hum. Reprod.* 8, 871–879. <https://doi.org/10.1093/molehr/8.9.871>

560 Chen, C.H., Wang, S.W., Chen, C.W., Huang, M.R., Hung, J.S., Huang, H.C., Lin, H.H., Chen,
561 R.J., Shyu, M.K., Huang, M.C., 2013. MUC20 overexpression predicts poor prognosis and
562 enhances EGF-induced malignant phenotypes via activation of the EGFR-STAT3 pathway
563 in endometrial cancer. *Gynecol. Oncol.* 128, 560–567.

564 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygyno.2012.12.012>

565 Chen, J., Roan, N., 2015. Isolation and Culture of Human Endometrial Epithelial Cells and
566 Stromal Fibroblasts. *BIO-PROTOCOL* 5. <https://doi.org/10.21769/BioProtoc.1623>

567 Chen, J.C., Hoffman, J.R., Arora, R., Perrone, L.A., Gonzalez-Gomez, C.J., Vo, K.C., Laird,
568 D.J., Irwin, J.C., Giudice, L.C., 2016. Cryopreservation and recovery of human endometrial
569 epithelial cells with high viability, purity, and functional fidelity. *Fertil. Steril.* 105, 501–
570 510.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2015.10.011>

571 Chen, S.T., Kuo, T.C., Liao, Y.Y., Lin, M.C., Tien, Y.W., Huang, M.C., 2018. Silencing of
572 MUC20 suppresses the malignant character of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma cells
573 through inhibition of the HGF/MET pathway. *Oncogene* 1–13.
574 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41388-018-0403-0>

575 Corfield, A., 2017. Eukaryotic protein glycosylation: a primer for histochemists and cell
576 biologists. *Histochem. Cell Biol.* 147, 119–147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00418-016-1526-4>

577 Corfield, A.P., 2015. Mucins: A biologically relevant glycan barrier in mucosal protection.
578 *Biochim. Biophys. Acta - Gen. Subj.* 1850, 236–252.
579 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2014.05.003>

580 Dharmaraj, N., Chapela, P.J., Morgado, M., Hawkins, S.M., Lessey, B.A., Young, S.L., Carson,
581 D.D., 2014. Expression of the transmembrane mucins, MUC1, MUC4 and MUC16, in
582 normal endometrium and in endometriosis. *Hum. Reprod.* 29, 1730–1738.
583 <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/deu146>

584 Díaz-Gimeno, P., Horcajadas, J.A., Martinez-Conejero, J.A., Esteban, F.J., Alama, P., Pellicer,
585 A., Simon, C., 2011. A genomic diagnostic tool for human endometrial receptivity based on
586 the transcriptomic signature. *Rev. Iberoam. Fertil. y Reprod. Humana* 27, 337–351.
587 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2010.04.063>

588 Enders, A.C., Hendrickx, A.G., Schlafke, S., 1983. Implantation in the rhesus monkey: Initial
589 penetration of endometrium. *Am. J. Anat.* 167, 275–298.
590 <https://doi.org/10.1002/aja.1001670302>

591 Evans, G.E., Phillipson, G.T.M., Sin, I.L., Frampton, C.M.A., Kirker, J.A., Bigby, S.M., Evans,
592 J.J., 2012. Gene expression confirms a potentially receptive endometrium identified by
593 histology in fertile women. *Hum. Reprod.* 27, 2747–2755.
594 <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/des233>

595 Fuhrich, D.G., Lessey, B.A., Savaris, R.F., 2013. Comparison of HSCORE Assessment of
596 Endometrial β 3 Integrin Subunit Expression with Digital HSCORE Using Computerized
597 Image Analysis (ImageJ). *Anal Quant Cytopathol Histopathol* 35, 210–216.
598 <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl061786n.Core-Shell>

599 Germeyer, A., Savaris, R.F., Jauckus, J., Lessey, B., 2014. Endometrial beta3 Integrin profile
600 reflects endometrial receptivity defects in women with unexplained recurrent pregnancy
601 loss. *Reprod. Biol. Endocrinol.* 12, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1477-7827-12-53>

602 Gipson, I.K., Blalock, T., Tisdale, A., Spurr-Michaud, S., Allcorn, S., Stavreus-Evers, A.,
603 Gemzell, K., 2008. MUC16 Is Lost from the Uterodome (Pinopode) Surface of the
604 Receptive Human Endometrium: In Vitro Evidence That MUC16 Is a Barrier to
605 Trophoblast Adherence¹. *Biol. Reprod.* 78, 134–142.
606 <https://doi.org/10.1095/biolreprod.106.058347>

607 Haouzi, D., Mahmoud, K., Fourar, M., Bendhaou, K., Dechaud, H., De Vos, J., Rème, T.,
608 Dewailly, D., Hamamah, S., 2009. Identification of new biomarkers of human endometrial
609 receptivity in the natural cycle. *Hum. Reprod.* 24, 198–205.
610 <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/den360>

611 Hatrup, C.L., Gendler, S.J., 2008. Structure and Function of the Cell Surface (Tethered) Mucins.

612 Annu. Rev. Physiol. 70, 431–457.
613 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.physiol.70.113006.100659>

614 Hertig, A.T., Rock, J., Adams, E.C., 1956. A description of 34 human ova within the first 17
615 days of development. *Am. J. Anat.* 98, 435–493. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aja.1000980306>

616 Hey, N.A., Graham, R.A., Seif, M.W., Aplin, J.D., 1994. The polymorphic epithelial mucin
617 MUC1 in human endometrium is regulated with maximal expression in the implantation
618 phase. *J. Clin. Endocrinol. and Metab.* 337–342.
619 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1210/jcem.78.2.8106621>

620 Higuchi, T., Orita, T., Katsuya, K., Yamasaki, Y., Akiyama, K., Li, H., Yamamoto, T., Saito, Y.,
621 Nakamura, M., 2004a. MUC20 suppresses the hepatocyte growth factor-induced Grb2-Ras
622 pathway by binding to a multifunctional docking site of met. *Mol. Cell. Biol.* 24, 7456–
623 7468. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MCB.24.17.7456-7468.2004>

624 Higuchi, T., Orita, T., Nakanishi, S., Katsuya, K., Watanabe, H., Yamasaki, Y., Waga, I.,
625 Nanayama, T., Yamamoto, Y., Munger, W., Sun, H.W., Falk, R.J., Jennette, J.C., Alcorta,
626 D.A., Li, H., Yamamoto, T., Saito, Y., Nakamura, M., 2004b. Molecular Cloning, Genomic
627 Structure, and Expression Analysis of MUC20, a Novel Mucin Protein, Up-regulated in
628 Injured Kidney. *J. Biol. Chem.* 279, 1968–1979. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M304558200>

629 Hu, S., Yao, G., Wang, Y., Xu, H., Ji, X., He, Y., Zhu, Q., Chen, Z., Sun, Y., 2014.
630 Transcriptomic changes during the pre-receptive to receptive transition in human
631 endometrium detected by RNA-Seq. *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.* 99, E2744–E2753.
632 <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2014-2155>

633 Imai, K., Maeda, M., Fujiwara, H., Okamoto, N., Kariya, M., Emi, N., Takakura, K., Kanzaki,
634 H., Mori, T., 1992. Human endometrial stromal cells and decidual cells express cluster of
635 differentiation (CD) 13 antigen/aminopeptidase N and CD10 antigen/neutral endopeptidase.

- 636 Biol. Reprod. 46, 328–334.
- 637 Jeschke, U., Walzel, H., Mylonas, I., Papadopoulos, P., Shabani, N., Kuhn, C., Schulze, S.,
638 Friese, K., Karsten, U., Anz, D., Kupka, M.S., 2009. The human endometrium expresses the
639 glycoprotein mucin-1 and shows positive correlation for Thomsen-Friedenreich epitope
640 expression and galectin-1 binding. *J. Histochem. Cytochem.* 57, 871–881.
641 <https://doi.org/10.1369/jhc.2009.952085>
- 642 Katayama, S., Töhönen, V., Linnarsson, S., Kere, J., 2013. SAMstr: Statistical test for
643 differential expression in single-cell transcriptome with spike-in normalization.
644 *Bioinformatics* 29, 2943–2945. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btt511>
- 645 Kato, K., Yoshimoto, M., Kato, K., Adachi, S., Yamayoshi, A., Arima, T., Asanoma, K., Kyo,
646 S., Nakahata, T., Wake, N., 2007. Characterization of side-population cells in human
647 normal endometrium. *Hum. Reprod.* 22, 1214–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/del514>
- 648 Kosciński, I., Viville, S., Porchet, N., Bernigaud, A., Escande, F., Defossez, A., Buisine, M.P.,
649 2006. MUC4 gene polymorphism and expression in women with implantation failure. *Hum.*
650 *Reprod.* 21, 2238–2245. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/del189>
- 651 Krjutškov, K., Katayama, S., Saare, M., Vera-Rodriguez, M., Lubenets, D., Samuel, K., Laisk-
652 Podar, T., Teder, H., Einarsdottir, E., Salumets, A., Kere, J., 2016. Single-cell transcriptome
653 analysis of endometrial tissue. *Hum. Reprod.* 31, 844–853.
654 <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/dew008>
- 655 Kyo, S., Nakamura, M., Kiyono, T., Maida, Y., Kanaya, T., Tanaka, M., Yatabe, N., Inoue, M.,
656 2003. Successful immortalization of Endometrial Glandular Cells with Normal Structural
657 and Functional Characteristics. *Am. J. Pathol.* 163, 2259–2269.
658 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9440\(10\)63583-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9440(10)63583-3)
- 659 Li, J., Tibshirani, R., 2011. Finding consistent patterns: A nonparametric approach for

660 identifying differential expression in RNA-Seq data. *Stat. Methods Med. Res.* 22, 519–536.
661 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0962280211428386>

662 Livak, K.J., Schmittgen, T.D., 2001. Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time
663 quantitative PCR and the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method. *Methods* 25, 402–408.
664 <https://doi.org/10.1006/meth.2001.1262>

665 Masuda, A., Katoh, N., Nakabayashi, K., Kato, K., Sonoda, K., Kitade, M., Takeda, S., Hata, K.,
666 Tomikawa, J., 2016. An improved method for isolation of epithelial and stromal cells from
667 the human endometrium. *J. Reprod. Dev.* 62, 213–218. <https://doi.org/10.1262/jrd.2015-137>

668 Montesano, R., Matsumoto, K., Nakamura, T., Orci, L., 1991. Identification of a fibroblast-
669 derived epithelial morphogen as hepatocyte growth factor. *Cell* 67, 901–908.
670 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-8674\(91\)90363-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-8674(91)90363-4)

671 Noyes, R.W., Hertig, A.T., Rock, J., 1950. Dating the Endometrial Biopsy. *Fertil. Steril.* 1, 3–25.
672 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0015-0282\(16\)30062-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0015-0282(16)30062-0)

673 Psychoyos, A., 1986. Uterine Receptivity for Nidation. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 476, 36–42.
674 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.1986.tb20920.x>

675 Rubin, J.S., Chan, A.M., Bottaro, D.P., Burgess, W.H., Taylor, W.G., Cech, A.C., Hirschfield,
676 D.W., Wong, J., Miki, T., Finch, P.W., 1991. A broad-spectrum human lung fibroblast-
677 derived mitogen is a variant of hepatocyte growth factor. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 88,
678 415–9. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.88.2.415>

679 Schindelin, J., Arganda-Carreras, I., Frise, E., Kaynig, V., Longair, M., Pietzsch, T., Preibisch,
680 S., Rueden, C., Saalfeld, S., Schmid, B., Tinevez, J.Y., White, D.J., Hartenstein, V.,
681 Eliceiri, K., Tomancak, P., Cardona, A., 2012. Fiji: An open-source platform for biological-
682 image analysis. *Nat. Methods* 9, 676–682. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2019>

683 Sha, A.G., Liu, J.L., Jiang, X.M., Ren, J.Z., Ma, C.H., Lei, W., Su, R.W., Yang, Z.M., 2011.

684 Genome-wide identification of micro-ribonucleic acids associated with human endometrial
685 receptivity in natural and stimulated cycles by deep sequencing. *Fertil. Steril.* 96, 150–
686 155.e5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2011.04.072>

687 Talbi, S., Hamilton, A.E., Vo, K.C., Tulac, S., Overgaard, M.T., Dosiou, C., Le Shay, N.,
688 Nezhat, C.N., Kempson, R., Lessey, B.A., Nayak, N.R., Giudice, L.C., 2006. Molecular
689 phenotyping of human endometrium distinguishes menstrual cycle phases and underlying
690 biological processes in normo-ovulatory women. *Endocrinology* 147, 1097–1121.
691 <https://doi.org/10.1210/en.2005-1076>

692 Thathiah, A., Carson, D.D., 2002. Mucins and blastocyst attachment. *Rev. Endocr. Metab.*
693 *Disord.* 3, 87–96. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015446626671>

694 Zheng, F., Yu, H., Lu, J., 2019. High expression of MUC20 drives tumorigenesis and predicts
695 poor survival in endometrial cancer. *J. Cell. Biochem.* 1–8.
696 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcb.28466>

697

698

699

700

701

702

703

704

705

707
 708 **Figure 1** A simplified scheme of the different phases of the menstrual cycle showing the days
 709 when the samples were collected in this study. Endometrial biopsies were obtained on day 2 and
 710 8 after the luteinising hormone surge (LH+2 and LH+8) during the same cycle. Paired samples
 711 (LH+2 and LH+8) from ten women were used for whole tissue analyses and samples from 26
 712 different were used for endometrial epithelial and stromal cells analysis. Of the possible 104
 713 samples from 26 women the numbers suitable for RNA-Seq and further validation were 18 for
 714 LH+2 epithelium, 26 for LH+8 epithelium, 20 for LH+2 stroma and 22 for LH+8 stroma. For
 715 sorted cells' samples, CD9 was considered as an epithelial marker and CD13 as a stromal
 716 marker. Two separate biopsies were obtained on cycle day 12 and cycle day 19 for primary cell
 717 culture and following protein analysis. The number of samples analysed on indicated days is
 718 shown in brackets (n). LH – luteinising hormone, WB – Western blot.

719

720 **Figure 2** The levels of *MUC1* and *MUC20* mRNAs in sorted human endometrial cells based on
 721 our published RNA-seq dataset (GSE97929) (Altmäe et al., 2017). Early-secretory (LH+2) and
 722 mid-secretory (LH+8) endometrial epithelial (n=44) and stromal (n=42) cells were analysed. The
 723 Mann-Whitney' test was used to compare the gene expression changes between the samples.
 724 Results are presented as a boxplot diagram where median values are marked as black lines inside
 725 boxes, which show interquartile range.

726

727

728

729 **Figure 3** The levels of *MUC1* and *MUC20* mRNAs were validated by RT-qPCR. Early-
 730 secretory (LH+2) and mid-secretory (LH+8) endometrial epithelial (n=17) and stromal (n=17)
 731 cells or whole endometrial tissue samples (n=10) were analysed. The gene expression changes
 732 were subjected to Welch two-sample *t*-test. Results are presented as a boxplot diagram; median
 733 values are marked as black lines inside boxes, which show interquartile range.

734

735

736

737

738

739

A

B

740

741 **Figure 4** MUC20 protein is expressed in human endometrium. A – validation of an anti-MUC20

742 antibody in A431 cell line with three different siRNAs against MUC20. B – the expression of

743 MUC20 in primary cultured endometrial epithelial (n=2) and stromal (n=2) cells. Cells isolated
744 from cycle day 12 and 19 biopsies. The A431 cell line was used as a positive and MCF-7 cell
745 line as a negative control. The expression of actin was used as a loading control. Molecular
746 weight markers are given in kilodaltons on the right hand side.

747

748

749

750

751

752

753

754

755

756

757

758

759

760

761

762

763

n=6

765 **Figure 5** MUC20 protein expression and localisation in the endometrial tissue in early-secretory
766 (LH+2) and mid-secretory (LH+8) endometrium visualised using immunohistochemistry (n=6).
767 Tissue samples of six fertile volunteers were analysed in early-secretory and mid-secretory
768 phases of the menstrual cycle. Representative images of the MUC20 expression in the three
769 tissue samples in early-secretory (A, C, E) and mid-secretory (B, D, F) phases of the menstrual
770 cycle. Mouse IgG was used as an isotype control for both phases (G, H). The ground images of
771 the tissue contain 50 μm scale bars, and lower magnification images bordered by black line are
772 one-fourth magnification of the ground images. Semi-quantification of all
773 immunohistochemistry (n=6) results (I). Relative DAB signal intensity was measured with
774 ImageJ package Fiji and paired t-test was used to compare results (values are mean \pm SD). GE –
775 glandular epithelium, LE – luminal epithelium, and S – stroma.

776

777 **Figure 6** The levels of *HGF* and *MET* mRNAs in endometrial stromal and epithelial cells,
 778 respectively, based on our published RNA-seq data (Altmäe et al., 2017). Early-secretory
 779 (LH+2) and mid-secretory (LH+8) endometrial stromal (n=42) and epithelial (n=44) cells were
 780 analysed. The Mann-Whitney' test was used to compare the gene expression changes between
 781 the samples. Results are presented as a boxplot diagram where median values are marked as
 782 black lines inside boxes, which show interquartile range.

783

784

785

786

787 **Figure 7** An interaction of MUC20 with the MET receptor signalling. A – The interaction of
 788 MUC20 with the MET receptor blocks HGF-induced proliferation of epithelial cells, which was
 789 shown previously in the case of renal tubule epithelium (Higuchi et al., 2004a). B – A
 790 hypothetical model of MUC20 interaction with the MET receptor in the human endometrium
 791 during WOI. The expression of MUC20 and MET increase in the epithelial cells at LH+8, with
 792 the concomitant increase of HGF expression in stromal cells. This regulation by MUC20 may
 793 prove to be important for the successful preparation of the endometrium for embryo
 794 implantation.

795

796 **Table 1** Expression of different mucin mRNAs in human endometrial epithelial and stromal
 797 cells.

	<i>MUC1</i>	<i>MUC4</i>	<i>MUC6</i>	<i>MUC7</i>	<i>MUC13</i>	<i>MUC15</i>	<i>MUC20</i>	<i>MUC22</i>
Epithelium LH+2	15/18 (83.3%)	1/18 (5.6%)	0/18 (0%)	0/18 (0%)	4/18 (22.2%)	8/18 (44.4%)	5/18 (27.8%)	3/18 (16.7%)
Epithelium LH+8	24/26 (92.3%)	3/26 (11.5%)	0/26 (0%)	1/26 (3.8%)	14/26 (53.8%)	11/26 (42.3%)	23/26 (88.5%)	1/26 (3.8%)
Stroma LH+2	9/20 (45%)	0/20 (0%)	1/20 (5%)	0/20 (0%)	1/20 (5%)	3/20 (15%)	2/20 (10%)	4/20 (20%)
Stroma LH+8	12/22 (54.5%)	0/22 (0%)	0/22 (0%)	0/22 (0%)	1/22 (4.5%)	4/22 (18.2%)	10/22 (45.5%)	2/22 (9.1%)

798

799 Data are based on the published cell-type specific RNA-seq (GSE97929) data (Altmäe et al.,
 800 2017). For each tissue sample, the ratio of positive samples (detected/analysed) and the
 801 percentage of positive samples that express the indicated mucin are shown in the upper and
 802 lower row, respectively.

803

804